

Physical Activity is the Main Factor of a Healthy Lifestyle

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Abstract: It was mentioned based on scientific sources that the basis of health maintenance is movement, how active a person is, it serves to prolong the life of a person. It is recommended to do physical exercises systematically. This article aims to study physical activity as the main factor in a healthy lifestyle using the works of our great scholars.

Keywords: physical activity, exercise, health, physical education, physical movement, activity, disease, walking, loading.

Introduction

To form a healthy lifestyle in our society, to create conditions for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, to strengthen the confidence of young people in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, large-scale work is being carried out aimed at developing the feelings of bravery and patriotism, loyalty to the motherland, as well as systematic organization of selection of talented athletes from among young people, as well as further development of physical education and mass sports. We know very well that our compatriot Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), a great scholar, encyclopedist scientist, sultan of medical science, created many of his works in the field of medicine, but the main basis of his works are the factors that cause diseases. In today's terms, health is no exaggeration to say that the foundations of a healthy lifestyle have been acquired. Ibn Sina put physical education and good physical activity in the first place in health measures, and diet and sleep in the second and third places. The scientist was the first to scientifically substantiate the fact that physical exercises strengthen the human body. Ibn Sina divided physical exercises into small and large, very strong and weak, fast and slow and slow types. He considered physical training to be the main factor in maintaining human health. According to him: - the body should be clean before the body engages in physical exercises; - the consumed food must be digested and, in turn, it is not recommended to perform physical exercises on an empty stomach; - a person who regularly engages in moderate physical exercises will not need any treatment; - physical education is an action that forces a person to breathe deeply and continuously; - after physical training, one should immediately dive into cold water until it covers the whole body. He stated that if the water does not harm the bather, he remains in the water until his body trembles. Today is the time when every person strengthens his health by improving physical culture. Physical activity is one of the conditions of hormonal formation of a young organism and prevents arteriosclerosis. In America, they believe that in order to achieve great success in life, it is necessary to be healthy, strong, and beautiful first of all. In England, they think that a young person's achievement in sports is more important than academic achievement. In Japan, people who quit smoking and

don't use elevators are charged extra. A decrease in physical activity reduces mental activity, because the impulses from the muscles to the brain are reduced. Therefore, a person becomes angry and nervous. With physical exercises, all organs of a person are well supplied with oxygen, leukocytes in the blood increase, and diseases are less common. It is known that people who regularly do physical exercises consult a doctor 4 times less than ordinary people. Most people walk to work, and when they do, they walk often. Walking is the most natural, normal movement, and it is also the most comfortable type of physical activity. When we walk, our muscles do what they have done all their lives. According to physiologists, walking does not put a big load on the body. When walking, the heart exercises mental, blood circulation accelerates. Walking is very useful for people who do work. Walking should be started an hour and a half before or after eating. Running is very beneficial for obese people. When running, breathing volume increases, blood vessels expand. When you do little exercise for a long time, the consumption of bioenergy in the body decreases, the size of the heart expands, its contractions are not effective for it, and the endurance of the vascular system decreases. Tissues do not receive oxygen, it becomes difficult for metabolic products to leave tissues. The amount of erythrocyte hemoglobin in the blood decreases. Changes also occur in the muscular system, muscles become smaller, protein synthesis is disturbed.

Literature Analysis and Methodology

I.I. Mechnikov, A.A. Bogomols, D.F. Chebotarev, A.N. Nagornky, I.V. Davudovsky and others were involved. Aging (senescence) is a legitimate biological process, the vital functions of the body decrease. In old age, our body begins to dry, heat decreases, and the body becomes dehydrated.

As early as the 18th century, the famous French doctor Tissot wrote: "All the medicines in the world cannot affect the body as well as when they are used." The physical load that falls on the body every day exercises the body's muscles, veins and nervous system, always gives it freshness and agility, increases the body's strength and working capacity.

Regardless of a person's age, gender, living conditions, and lifestyle, if he does not engage in physical education, he will destroy his body.

In Uzbekistan, all conditions have been created for residents to engage in physical exercises and sports. Especially young people are engaged in various types of physical exercises and sports. Sports competitions are held every year. They are making great progress in boxing, wrestling, karate, and taekwondo sports of Uzbekistan.

Since ancient times, mankind has tried to live as long as possible, while maintaining health and working capacity. Everyone knows that satisfaction with work, physical activity, exposure to fresh air, moderate nutrition, rest and other things allow a person to live a long and healthy life. Long-lived people suffer not only from congenital diseases, but also from diseases acquired during their lifetime.

According to Joan Collins, our life is like a play in three acts. The first act is from birth to 30 years - youth. The second act is from 30 to 60 years old - the age of maturity. The third act is after 60.

The third act, the most interesting in the theater, is the change in biological processes during life that leads to aging. According to Galen, old age is not a disease, but a state between health and illness.

Results

Ibn Sina divided the age of people into 4 periods. Age of growth up to 30 years old - the period of youth from 35-40 to 60 years old - the period of maturity. The period of old age begins after the age of 60. Studies of ethnographic factors reveal several hypotheses about longevity: "work", "food" and others. Maintaining the health of the elderly is important in social life. The content of a healthy lifestyle consists of work and rest, sleep hygiene, food

hygiene, physical exercises, self-respect, self-control in relationships with people, etc. Ibn Sina also attached great importance to the process of building the organism by using natural forces - air, water and sun, with physical exercises. According to him, walking for a long time in the open air, finding the body, moving, walking, playing games along with physical exercises will have a good effect.

Conclusion

Physical activity is one of the main factors of living a healthy life until the end of our life, it does not choose age, place, or even conditions. It has many appearances, forms, and methods. There are types of yoga, pilates, walking, running, pull-ups, athletics, dancing, rafting, bodybuilding, gymnastics, football, etc. Choose what you want, as long as you are physically active. If you do sports for 30-60 minutes not every day, it is enough for you to be healthy. You need to sit less and move more. If your job requires you to sit down, take a break of at least 5 minutes every hour and do various light exercises during this time to tone your shoulders, back and legs.

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